

Improving the control of sodium accumulation in closed-loop soilless culture systems using ion selective electrodes and the DSS NUTRISENSE

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Abstract

The management of sodium accumulation in the recycled drainage solution (DS) is a major challenge in closed-loop soilless culture systems (CLS). Currently, this problem is addressed through complete or periodic discharge of the DS. An attractive alternative approach is to compensate for sodium accumulation by reducing the concentrations of macronutrients in the DS, thus maintaining a target electrical conductivity without or with minimal DS discharge. By employing ion selective electrodes (ISEs) to directly measure macronutrient concentrations in the DS, this strategy can be much more effectively implemented, as the risk of nutrient depletion is minimised. To evaluate the efficiency of the new strategy and the performance of the ISEs, an experiment with cucumber crop and three treatments was conducted. The plants were grown in one open soilless system and one CLS, with standard nutrient management and one CLS where the new strategy in salinity management was applied. The irrigation water had 2.5 mM of Na⁺. In the control CLS, a NS with a standard composition was supplied throughout the cropping period. In the ISE treatment, the NO₃⁻, K⁺, Ca²⁺, and Na⁺ concentrations in the DS were daily measured using LAQUAtwin ISEs (Horiba, Kyoto, Japan), while EC and pH were also daily measured using portable instruments, and Mg²⁺ and SO₄²⁻ were calculated using the measured data. The data obtained from these measurements were subsequently introduced into NUTRISENSE to calculate a readjusted NS composition and the injection rates of single-salt fertilisers that are necessary for its implementation. The LAQUAtwin ISEs proved to be highly accurate and the measured EC, pH, NO₃⁻, K⁺, Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ concentrations in the DS were maintained close to the readjusted target values. The results show that the strategy to reduce the nutrient concentrations in the root zone to compensate for sodium accumulation by daily readjusting the supplied NS composition using data from ISE measurements, is efficient and scalable for commercial application.

Keywords: Cucumber, salinity, hydroponics, nutrient recirculation, nutrient management

INTRODUCTION

Closed-loop soilless culture systems (CLS) constitute a sustainable form of greenhouse vegetable production as the recycling of the drainage solution (DS) reduces substantially the consumption of water and nutrients. Adoption of these cropping systems in greenhouses can

effectively contribute to achieving the EU Green Deal's goals, of 50% less nutrient losses associated with a 20% reduction of fertiliser use by 2030. CLS can reduce water and fertiliser consumption by up to 30% and 40% (Singh et al., 2019), and prevent pollution of aquifers with nitrates and phosphates (Giannothanasis et al., 2024a). However, the adoption of CLS can be limited due to sodium (Na^+) accumulation in the DS originating from the raw water used to prepare nutrient solution (NS), thereby exposing the crop to salinity stress (Savvas et al., 2005a). Strategies to mitigate Na^+ accumulation typically include partial DS discharge (Katsoulas et al., 2015) or maintaining the EC in the DS to safe levels by reducing nutrient concentrations in the DS to equivalent levels with the Na increase (Voogt et al., 2023; Giannothanasis et al., 2024b).

Decision Support Systems (DSS) specialty designed for CLS could minimise or even eliminate the need to discharge DS, thus avoiding nutrient losses and environmental impacts while ensuring an optimal nutrient status in the root environment of the crop. To maximise the performance of a DSS for CLSs, models and algorithms utilising sensor measurements are required. Ion selective electrodes (ISEs) are sensors that can be used to measure ion concentrations in nutrient solution samples (Han et al., 2020) using an ion-selective membrane. The NUTRISENSE DSS, which has been developed for nutrient management in soilless culture, already has a specific function to receive and process data obtained from ISEs and provide advice about the necessary changes in the fertigation formula (Giannothanasis et al., 2024a). The NUTRISENSE DSS deploys a series of special algorithms considering not only the technical characteristics of the ISEs, but also the complex chemistry of the NSs, as well as the plant nutrient requirements. Furthermore, the NUTRISENSE DSS comprises special algorithms to manage Na accumulation in the DS by commensurate adjustments in the target nutrient concentrations, thus preventing exposure of the crop to salinity stress (Giannothanasis et al., 2024b).

In the current study, the efficiency of the NUTRISENSE DSS to manage the accumulation of Na was tested in a closed-loop soilless cultivation of cucumber, in which the Na concentration in the raw water used to prepare NS was suboptimal for use in CLS (2.5 mM). A specific objective of the current study was to test the efficiency of the DSS and the ISEs to maintain the target nutrient concentrations in the root zone and the yield potential compared with both an open system without recycling and a CLS without the use of ISEs. A further objective of the study was to quantify the nutrient losses in the open system, which constitute the savings of nutrients and water achieved in the CLS due to recycling of the DS.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Outline of the ISE/NUTRISENSE technology

The strategy tested in the current study is based on daily determination of key macronutrient concentrations in the DS using ion selective electrodes (ISEs), and entering the measured data to the DSS NUTRISENSE for automatic determination of the fertiliser injection rates based on the measurements of the ISEs. This strategy has been tested also in a previous study with a tomato crop (Giannothanasis et al., 2024b). However, in that study the raw water used to prepare NS was of good quality with a Na^+ concentration of only 0.5 mM and thus its accumulation to the system was very low. In the current study, the same strategy was applied in a cucumber crop, in which the Na^+ concentration in the raw water was substantially higher (2.5 mM), resulting in substantial Na^+ accumulation in the DS. To cope with the Na^+ accumulation, the target nutrient concentrations in the DS were daily readjusted using the NUTRISENSE DSS to levels compensating for the Na^+ increase, thereby avoiding an increase of the total ionic concentration as indicated by the EC, thereby avoiding salt stress. The daily readjustment was

based on the measurement of the NO_3^- , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , and Na^+ concentrations in the DS using the LAQUAtwin ISEs (Horiba, Kyoto, Japan). The aim of the daily readjustment was to maintain the macronutrient concentrations in the root solution (RS) and the DS close to the target levels suggested in the literature (Sonneveld and Voogt, 2009). The algorithm is based on a mass-balance equation for each nutrient, which aims to accurately calculate the addition of stock solution fertilisers in the system, considering the natural and chemical restrictions, and the available equipment in the greenhouse unit. The composition of the RS is considered similar with that of the DS (Blok et al., 2023) and, therefore, henceforth they are both referenced as RS/DS. Furthermore, the ratios between the net nutrient and water supply to the plants (mmol L^{-1}), excluding the resupply through the recycled DS, are considered concentrations of a NS termed added solution (AS), as suggested by Blok et al. (2023) and Savvas et al. (2024).

To readjust the nutrient supply, the DSS recalculates the concentration of each nutrient in the supplied solution (SS) aiming to restore its target concentration in the RS/DS. The daily readjustment of the SS composition is possible using fertigation systems with single fertiliser stock solutions which allow for preparing nutrient solutions with different composition merely by altering the injection rates of the stock solutions and the target EC. The most common fertigation systems of this type employ eight tanks for the fertilisers and one for the acid used for pH adjustment. The fertilisers used for SS preparation were calcium nitrate, potassium nitrate, ammonium nitrate, magnesium nitrate, magnesium sulphate, potassium sulphate, monopotassium phosphate, iron chelate and nitric acid. The micronutrients Mn, Zn, Cu, B, Mo were added at a standard ratio in the stock solution of monopotassium phosphate and thus their supply rates were not altered when readjusting the concentrations of major nutrients in relation to the ISEs measurements. The limitations in NS composition arising from the available fertilisers and nutrients within each single fertiliser were also taken into consideration when readjusting the AS.

Experimental design, plant growth and mineral analysis

To access the effectiveness of the strategy to manage Na^+ accumulation in CLS using ISE measurements and the DSS NUTRISENSE, a cucumber crop experiment was conducted. This study took place in a greenhouse at the Agricultural University of Athens, Laboratory of Vegetable Production (AUA: 37°58'54.2"N, 23°42'22.0"E, altitude 35 m). Twelve experimental plots were established, each consisting of a 5-meter gutter with five coconut-fiber slabs ($1 \times 0.2 \times 0.15\text{m}$), and these were randomly assigned into one of the following three treatments. The first treatment was an open soilless system where the DS was rejected. The second treatment was a CLS where all the volume of DS was collected and recycled. In these two treatments, nutrient adjustment followed the standard method of fortnightly adjusting the composition of the supplied NS using the DSS NUTRISENSE, after an analysis of the DS (Savvas et al., 2023), while the nutrient levels in the root environment were maintained constant up to targets suggested in credible literature sources (Sonneveld and Voogt, 2009). The third treatment, termed ISE/NUTRISENSE, was also a CLS, but the concentrations of K, Ca, Mg, NO_3^- , and SO_4^{2-} in the SS were daily readjusted based on the measurements of NO_3^- , K^+ , Ca^{2+} and Na^+ using the ISEs and the daily EC and pH measurements. In the ISE/NUTRISENSE treatment, the DSS did not use constant target concentrations for K, Ca, Mg, NO_3^- , and SO_4^{2-} in the DS as in the second treatment but readjusted these daily to levels compensating for the Na^+ accumulation, while maintaining their mutual molar ratios constant. This strategy has been tested also in a previous study (Giannothanas et al., 2024b). However, in that study, the readjustment was performed not daily but fortnightly based on analyses of the DS performed in a standard laboratory and not on daily measurements using ISE.

To establish the experiment, cucumber grafted seedlings (*Cucumis sativus* L. cv. Mainalos RZ F1 × Affyne RZ F1) were transplanted to coconut-fiber slabs on 27 March 2024 with a density of 2.4 plants m⁻². Nutrient solution (NS) supply and drainage solution (DS) recycling started on April 3, 2024 (day 0 after recycling initiation (DARI)), and the study was terminated on 13 July 2024 (101 DARI). Each plant was pruned to a single stem, which was descending when it reached the supporting wire height and, after full growth, the number of its leaves was maintained between 14 to 16 by weekly removing older leaves aiming to a target leaf area index (LAI) of 3-3.5. The composition of the raw water used for NS preparation was as follows: EC: 0.5 dS m⁻¹; pH 7.8; Ca²⁺ 0.9 mM; Mg²⁺ 0.3 mM; Na⁺ 2.5 mM; SO₄²⁻ 0.2 mM; Cl⁻ 2.3 mM; HCO₃⁻ 2.2 mM. The irrigation frequency was adjusted using a pyranometer. The accumulated solar radiation reached for each irrigation event was adjusted aiming to maintain the percentage of DS to around 30% of the total supplied NS. A fertigation system (ALAGRO, Athens, Greece) with nine tanks, each containing a stock solution of a single-salt fertiliser (calcium nitrate, potassium nitrate, ammonium nitrate, monopotassium phosphate, potassium sulfate, magnesium nitrate, magnesium sulfate, iron chelate, and nitric acid) was used for automated NS preparation after receiving online the injection ratios of each stock solution from NUTRISENSE. Micronutrients (Mn, Zn, Cu, B, Mo) were added to the stock solution of monopotassium phosphate.

Daily DS samples were collected from the ISE treatment, and the K⁺, Ca²⁺, NO₃⁻, and Na⁺ concentrations in it were measured by LAQUAtwin sensors (Horiba, Kyoto, Japan), while EC and pH were measured using the sensors HI98312 and HI8424, respectively, (Hanna Instr. Inc., Woonsocket RI, USA). The Mg²⁺ and the SO₄²⁻ concentrations in the DS were daily estimated by NUTRISENSE using the equations of Savvas and Adamidis (1999, 2000), using the EC measurement of the day and the concentrations of the three macrocations (K⁺, Ca²⁺ and Na⁺) measured by the ISEs. The NUTRISENSE DSS, via ISE measurements, calculated and transmitted to the fertigation system daily adjustments to mixed DS with raw water to a target EC (E_m), and subsequently the added stock solutions of the eight fertilisers at injection rates, aiming to achieve the final target EC (E_s) in the outgoing SS.

The macronutrient levels in the DS were also determined by standard methods at fortnightly intervals. The K⁺, Na⁺, Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ concentrations were measured using an atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AA-7000, Shimadzu, Japan), while NO₃⁻ was quantified photometrically at 540 nm using a microplate spectrophotometer (Anthos Zenyth 200; Biochrom, UK), applying the vanadium chloride method (Schnetger and Lehnert, 2014). These measurements were used in T1 and T2 to readjust the composition of the SS at fortnight intervals, while in T3 they were used only to check the accuracy and reliability of the measures obtained from the ISEs.

Statistical analyses

The statistical analysis of the data was performed using the STATISTICA 12.5 for Windows (StatSoft Inc., Tulsa, USA) while the graphical representation of the data was carried out using the GraphPad Prism 8 software (GraphPad Software, USA).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 shows that the actual NO₃⁻ and K⁺ concentrations in the DS were in close alignment with the respective target values throughout the cropping period. In contrast, the NO₃⁻ and K⁺ concentrations in the AS and the SS calculated by NUTRISENSE exhibited wide daily fluctuations, which were anticyclic to the fluctuations of NO₃⁻ and K⁺ in the DS. This happened because the strategy of NUTRISENSE was to increase or decrease the supply of a nutrient each day to the

levels required to restore its concentration in the DS, when this was lower or higher, respectively, than the target value. Thus, for instance, when the concentration of NO_3^- in the DS was even slightly lower than the target value on that date, NUTRISENSE calculated an extra amount of NO_3^- input to increase the NO_3^- concentration in the DS to the target level within one day. Taking into consideration the current NO_3^- concentration in the DS, the volume of NS per plant in the system (mainly in the substrate) and the volume of net NS supply per day per plant, NUTRISENSE calculated a readjusted concentration of NO_3^- in the SS, and concomitantly in the AS. Since the adaptation had to be achieved within one day, the increase of the NO_3^- concentration in the SS (and concomitantly in the DS) was sometimes considerable compared to the standard according to the literature (e.g., Sonneveld and Voogt, 2009). The same approach was applied also when the NO_3^- concentration measured by the ISE in the DS was higher than the target, but in that case, NUTRISENSE had to calculate a lower NO_3^- concentration in the SS than that of the previous day, to reduce the NO_3^- concentration in the SS. The same concept was applied also for K^+ , Ca^{2+} , and Mg^{2+} , while the concentration of SO_4^{2-} was used to electrochemically balance the SS and the AS.

Figure 1. A: Daily course of the measured and target NO_3^- concentrations in the drainage solution (DS), the supplied solution (SS) and the added solution (AS) in the ISE-NUTRISENSE treatment. B: Daily course of measured and target K^+ concentrations in the DS, the SS and the AS of the ISE-NUTRISENSE treatment. C: Daily course of Na^+ concentration in the DS of the three treatments. D: Daily course of the electrical conductivity (EC) in the DS of the three treatments.

As the plants only interact with the RS, the rapid corrections of any deviations from the target value in the RS/DS within one day is a substantial advantage in nutrient management. Furthermore, the accumulation of Na^+ in the RS/DS (Fig. 1C) due to full recycling of the DS,

stabilized at the level of 13 mM in both CLSs. As explained in a previous paper (Savvas et al., 2005a), this indicates that a concentration of 13 mM Na⁺ in the RS/DS imposed an uptake concentration of 2.5 mM Na⁺ and thus no further accumulation occurred. In the open system, the Na⁺ concentration stabilised at significantly lower levels as part of Na⁺ was discharged through the rejection of the DS (Fig. 1C). The similar threshold of Na⁺ accumulation in the two treatments with CLSs is reasonable, as in both treatments no DS was discharged, and the plants were growing under the same environmental conditions. In the NUTRISENSE-ISE treatment, the Na⁺ accumulation was successfully compensated by reducing the macronutrient concentrations in the RS as the EC was maintained close to the optimal value of 2.93 dS m⁻¹, similarly with the open system (Fig. 1D). However, in the CLS with standard management the EC increased to 4 dS m⁻¹ due to Na⁺ accumulation.

Figure 2. Total yield per plant (kg), mean fruit weight (g) and number of fruits per plant in the three different treatments. Vertical bars denote \pm standard errors of means and different letters at each sampling date denote significant differences according to ANOVA test and Duncan's multiple range test ($p \leq 0.05$).

The increase of the EC in the CLS treatment with the standard management reduced the total yield by 13.2% compared to the open system, while in the NUTRISENSE-ISE treatment the yield was not affected. The reduction in yield occurred due to decreases in both the number of fruits per plant and the mean fruit weight. The yield reduction was a clear effect of salinity as the percentage of reduction per unit of EC increase beyond the upper threshold of 2.93 dS m⁻¹ is in alignment with that reported by Savvas et al. (2005b). This conclusion is also in agreement with the absence of any yield decrease in the NUTRISENSE-ISE treatment despite the lower nutrient levels and the higher Na⁺ in the root zone, which indicates that the yield responded to the EC level rather than to the Na⁺ concentration or the nutrient levels. Sonneveld and van der Burg (1991) suggested that nutrient concentrations in the RS/DS corresponding to 1.5 dS m⁻¹ are sufficient for satisfactory nutrition of cucumber provided that the mutual nutrient ratios are optimal. The implementation of the NUTRISENSE-ISE concept eliminated the risk of nutrient depletion in the root zone (Kempkes and Stanghellini, 2003; Voogt et al., 2023) and ensured a balanced nutrition.

No significant differences in fruit yield between the open system and the NUTRISENSE-ISE treatment, was observed as the plants were not exposed to excessive EC levels. However, in the open system the discharge of the DS resulted in huge nutrient losses ranging from 30% for K to 67.5% for Mg (Table 1).

Table 1. Nutrient losses (kg ha⁻¹) and percentage of nutrients lost due to discharge of the DS, with reference to the total nutrient supply (losses/ supply %) in the open system treatment.

Nutrient	N	P	K	Ca	Mg	S
Losses (Kg ha ⁻¹)	400.8	49.9	471.6	362.7	112.6	143.2
Losses / Supply (%)	37.4	30.3	30.0	44.4	67.5	53.7

As the drainage fraction was maintained close to 30% of the supply, the nutrients routinely maintained at substantially higher concentrations in the DS than in the SS (Ca, Mg, S) exhibited higher nutrient losses. In contrast, the losses of N, P and K, which routinely are present at slightly higher or even similar concentration in the DS and SS, were not substantially higher than 30%. As also reported in previous papers, the average nutrient losses occurring in open systems are between 30 and 50% of the total supply (Grewal et al., 2010; Massa et al., 2011), resulting in lower nutrient use efficiency, substantial nutrient emissions to the environment and considerably higher fertiliser consumption compared to those occurring in CLS. The nutrient emissions, and especially those of N and P, have serious environmental impacts, such as pollution of the drinking water and eutrophication of the surface water. Furthermore, the higher fertiliser consumption increases the energy costs and the greenhouse gas emissions, while reducing the economic viability of the greenhouse unit.

CONCLUSIONS

The proposed strategy utilizing ISE measurements to daily adjust nutrient supply through the DSS NUTRISENSE was successfully validated in a cucumber crop grown in a closed-loop system under saline conditions. The performance of the algorithms deployed by the NUTRISENSE DSS were confirmed also under salinity conditions. This approach supports a broader adoption of CLS in cucumber crops without compromising the yield performance and the nutritional status of the crop, even when the Na⁺ concentration in the raw water used to prepare NS is as high as 2.5mM. As a result, the use of ISEs in combination with a suitable DSS to properly utilise the data obtained from the ISEs, offers an environmentally and economically sustainable solution for greenhouse vegetable production.

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